

Physical meaning of transformation equations between two reference frames

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ABSTRACT

When time is an independent variable, the time is physical time, which is defined by physics; when time is a dependent variable, the time is mathematical time, which is defined by an equation. When a frame is selected as reference frame, the frame is a stationary frame, and other frames are moving frames. The two-frame setup we usually use for transformation is only for one-dimensional motion. Above three points is what we discussed in this paper since they are easily confused.

In this paper, we state the necessary and sufficient conditions to verify the correctness of transformation equations between two reference frames. This criterion is based on the concept and physical meaning of transformation between two reference frames. It is important to clarify the physical meaning of transformation and verify whether a transformation equation is correct; otherwise, it will lead to various surprising conclusions due to misconception.

This paper also explains why Galilean transformation does not apply to electromagnetic motion, the physical meaning of Lorentz covariance and the relationship between Lorentz covariance and the principle of relativity. This paper is a preparation for our next three papers.

KEYWORD

Lorentz transformation; Galilean transformation; special relativity; space and time; covariance; Maxwell; physics.

First of all, let us explain what the Galilean transformation is. Referring to Fig.1, if you are standing one side of a moving walkway in London Airport and trying to figure out the relative speed between yourself and a football running on the moving walkway, there are two methods to get the answer.

The first method is direct measurement. You can set yourself as the origin of a stationary frame S to measure the distance interval between yourself and the football and time interval, using a standard clock and a standard ruler. And then, you can get the football speed in the stationary frame S as per the speed definition:

$$u = \Delta x / \Delta t \tag{1}$$

Please note that when you use this method, the measurement of the football speed u in the stationary frame S is independent of the speed (v) of the moving walkway. The time interval you use is the physical time interval, which is based on the standard clock at Greenwich, London. The distance you measure is the physical distance, which is based on the standard length defined by physics.

Similarly, an observer standing on the moving walkway S' can also measure the relative speed between the observer and the football, i.e. the speed (u') of the football in the moving frame S' . It is very clear that the observer must use the same standard clock and standard ruler as you do; otherwise the speed u' has no physical meaning. The physical time and physical distance in the walkway frame S' are independent of the speed v , which is a relative speed between frame S' and S (the frame S is moving in $-v$ direction), and the speed u' is independent of any observing from any frame reference. As per the speed definition, the speed of the football in the walkway frame S' is:

$$u' = \Delta x' / \Delta t' \tag{2}$$

The second method is to apply a mathematical formula to figure out the speed u . If you know the speed (v) of the moving walkway and the football speed (u') in the moving frame S' , can you figure out the football speed (u) in the stationary frame S (the airport floor)? You must ensure the result is exactly the same as direct measurement, i.e. Eq.(1). You might say this is simple: the answer is to superimpose two speeds.

$$u = u' + v$$

The above equation is called inverse Galilean speed transform. However, this answer is not correct. Why? Let us explain how the Galilean transformation is derived. Please note that the sample of Fig.1 assumes there is no friction force between the football and the moving walkway.

1. The derivation of Galilean transformation

Fig.2 is a simple set up for transformation between two inertia reference frames $S(x, t, u)$ and $S'(x', t', u')$. We set the airport floor as a stationary frame $S(x, t, u)$ and moving walkway as a moving frame $S'(x', t', u')$. The setting of S' and S is exactly identical. The time axes and displacement axes are one-to-one correspondence. The words moving and stationary are equivalent. When you observe particle Q in frame S' (the moving walkway), the frame S' is stationary while

FIG. 1
MOVING WALKWAY

Fig. 2

the frame S (the airport floor) is moving.

Please note that there is no an absolute stationary reference frame in the universe. All motions are relative. The reference frame in which the observer is located is a stationary frame, such as the earth. We can designate a frame as stationary reference frame, such as the sun.

If the frame S is selected as reference frame, in which the observer is located, the symbol t represents the physical time, and the rate of the unit time interval is constant. The x displacement represents the physical distance, and the unit distance interval is constant. We usually locate the origin of frame S at point $x=0, t=0$, so t is time interval and x is distance interval. After the frame S is selected as reference frame, the frame S' is a moving frame. The variables t' and x' are not independent. t' is a function of t, x, v , i.e. $t' = f(x, t, v)$, and x' is a function of t, x, v , i.e. $x' = f(x, t, v)$. Therefore, t' is mathematical time, and x' is mathematical distance. On the other hand, if we select frame S' as reference frame, the frame S is moving. The variables t and x are mathematical and dependent while t' and x' are independent, i.e. $t = f(x', t', v')$, $x = f(x', t', v')$.

See Fig.2. If we know the speed u of a particle Q in reference frame S and the speed v of frame S' , can we figure out the speed u' of the particle Q in frame S' ? From the geometric relationship, we get [2]:

$$x' = x - vt$$

Inserting speed definition, $u' = x'/t'$, $u = x/t$, we get

$$u' = (u - v)t/t'$$

Since we don't know the mathematical relationship between t' and t , u' cannot be obtained.

However, Galilean postulated $t'=t$, thus

$$u' = u - v$$

In summary, the Galilean transformation equations are as follows:

$$x' = x - vt \tag{3}$$

$$t' = t \tag{4}$$

$$u' = u - v \tag{5}$$

By moving the variables, we can get the Galilean inverse transformation:

$$x = x' + vt' \tag{6}$$

$$t = t' \tag{7}$$

$$u = u' + v \tag{8}$$

The physical meaning of the Galilean transformation: If the speed u of a particle in reference frame S is known, we can calculate the speed u' of the particle in frame S' as per Eq.(5). The mathematical distance of the particle displacement in frame S' is as per Eq.(3). The mathematical time of the particle motion in frame S' is as per Eq.(4). On the other hand, if we know the physical x', t', u' , we can figure out the mathematical x, t, u as per Eq.(6), (7),(8).

It is clear that the mathematical values of x', t', u' as per Eq.(3), (4), (5) must be equal to the measurement values of x', t', u' in frame S' . If not, the Eq.(3),(4),(5) are not correct or are not useful.

Obviously, there is no nature relationship of time or distance between frames S' and S unless we set one of frames as reference frame to describe the motion trajectory of a particle in another frame. For example, a passenger traveling on a train may has a watch, which the time rate is different from the standard time, but the speed of the train does not affect the watch (which are called time) at all.

Since the equation $t'=t$ is an unconfirmed hypothesis, the Galilean transformation and Newtonian mechanics are labeled as absolute space-time. In fact, we can say that the Galilean time or speed transformation is not correct, but we cannot say Newtonian mechanics is based on an

absolute reference frame. Newtonian mechanics is based on physical time and physical space, not based on the explanations of natural time and natural space by Newton.

2. The defects of the Galilean transformation.

In 1632, Galileo described the Galilean invariance, i.e. the principle of Galilean relativity. Galilean relativity states that the laws of motion are the same in all inertial frames. Is the Galilean transformation compatible with the Galilean relativity principle? Let's discuss it.

In 1862, Maxwell's equations were published, and Maxwell first proposed that light is an electromagnetic phenomenon, and light speed is a constant and independent of reference frame. Maxwell's law is a part of Maxwell's equations, and it can be written as [4] :

$$\nabla \times \vec{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad (10)$$

Where \vec{B} is magnetic field, \vec{E} is electric field, ϵ_0 and μ_0 are constants, c is the speed of light.

Eq.(10) shows that the speed of light is a constant, which is independent of frame of reference. This postulate is confirmed by the Michelson and Morley experiment in 1887. Michelson and Morley experiment showed that the speed of light is independent of the motion state of a reference frame. It proved that ether does not exist, and there is no an absolute stationary frame in the universe.

If we consider photon motion as a particle motion, according to equation (5), we get

$$c' = c - v, \text{ when a photon moves in the positive direction along the } x\text{-axis} \quad (11)$$

$$c' = c + v, \text{ when a photon moves in the negative direction along the } x\text{-axis} \quad (12)$$

The Eq.(11), (12) indicate that the speed of light depends on a reference frame. If we apply Galilean speed transformation, i.e. Eq.(5), to transform the Maxwell's law from frame S to frame S', we get

$$\nabla' \times \vec{B}' = \frac{1}{(c-v)^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}'}{\partial t'} \quad (13)$$

$$\nabla' \times \vec{B}' = \frac{1}{(c+v)^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}'}{\partial t'} \quad (14)$$

According to the Galilean relativity, if Eq.(9) (Maxwell's law) is transformed from frame S to frame S', the Maxwell's law should remain unchanged:

$$\nabla' \times \vec{B}' = \frac{1}{c'^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}'}{\partial t'} \quad (15)$$

Comparing Eq.(13), (14) with Eq.(15), it indicates that for electromagnetic motion, Galilean transformation is incompatible with the Galilean relativity principle. Therefore, the Galilean transformation does not suitable to electromagnetic motion, or directly says the Galilean transformation is incorrect.

Due to above reason, Einstein published his famous paper in 1905, entitled "On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies". Einstein derived a new transformation called Lorentz transformation to replace the Galilean transformation for solving the above problem. Based on the Lorentz transformation, Einstein created his theory of special relativity. Einstein proposed two postulates in the paper:

1) Postulate of the principle of relativity — the laws of physics are invariant (i.e. identical) in all inertial frames of reference.

2) Postulate of the invariance of light speed — the speed of light in a vacuum is the same for all observers, regardless of the motion of the light source or observer (i.e. $c' = c$).

Einstein proposed a speed transformation as follows:

$$u' = (u - v)/(1 - vu/c^2) \quad (16)$$

Einstein proposed a speed inverse transformation as follows:

$$u = (u' + v)/(1 + vu'/c^2) \quad (17)$$

Substituting $u = c$ into Eq.(16), we get

$$c' = (c - v)/(1 - vc/c^2) = c \quad \text{i.e. } c' = c$$

Substituting $u' = c'$ into Eq.(17), we get

$$c = (c' + v)/(1 + vc'/c'^2) = c' \quad \text{i.e. } c = c'$$

Therefore, the Lorentz transformation conforms to the postulate of the invariance of light speed.

Using the Lorentz transformation, we are able to transform Maxwell's law from frame S to frame S', and keep the Maxwell's law unchanged:

$$\nabla' \times \vec{B}' = \frac{1}{c'^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}'}{\partial t'} \quad (15)$$

Since Lorentz transformation conforms to the postulate of the principle of relativity for electromagnetic motion, the Lorentz transformation is considered to be applicable to electromagnetic motion and high energy physics.

In fact, we can guess that the Galilean time transformation, i.e. $t' = t$, is incorrect from Fig. 2. Since the coordinate unit intervals and time unit intervals of the frames S' and S are identical, the time reading t is proportional to the coordinate reading x : $t \propto x$. When $x \uparrow$, must be $t \uparrow$. Due to $x' < x$, it must be $t' < t$.

Also, from the definition of speed, we can know that the concept of speed superimposing is incorrect. If $t = t_1 + t_2$, $x = x_1 + x_2$, $u_1 = x_1/t_1$, $u_2 = x_2/t_2$, $u = x/t$, we have

$$u = (x_1 + x_2)/(t_1 + t_2) \neq (x_1/t_1) + (x_2/t_2) = u_1 + u_2$$

3. The physical meaning of Lorentz covariance

The concept of covariance is similar to the principle of relativity. That is, after transforming a particle motion from one reference frame to another reference frame by a group of transformation equations of two coordinate systems, the forms of physical formulas and the definitions or the concepts of the physical quantity remains unchanged. For example, the equation of Newton's second law in frame S is $F = m a$. Applying the Galilean transformation to transform the Newton's second law from frame S to frame S', the Newton's second law in frame S' can be written as: $F' = m' a'$. Since the form of Newton's second law remains unchanged after applying the Galilean transformation, it means that Newton's second law is Galilean covariant. The physical meaning of Galilean covariance, in this case, is that the Galilean transformation is compatible with the principle of relativity.

However, conforming to the principle of relativity is only the necessary condition to verify that the Galilean transformation is correct or to verify the equation $F = m a$ is correct, rather than the sufficient condition. In Section 2, we have pointed out the defects of the Galilean transformation. The equation $F = m a$ is not perfect, because the equation $F = m a$ is based on a postulate of mass invariance, which is incorrect when the speed of a particle is close to the speed of light.

Referring to Section 2, Maxwell's equations are not Galilean covariant, because after transforming Maxwell's equations from frame S to frame S' by the Galilean transformation, the forms of Maxwell's equations must be changed, which is not in accordance with the principle of relativity. It indicates that if Maxwell's equations are correct, the Galilean transformation is incorrect. Therefore, the Galilean transformation does not apply to electromagnetic motion. In order to provide new transformation equations between two reference frames, which is in accordance with the principle of relativity and applicable for electromagnetic motion, Einstein derived Lorentz transformation [1]:

$$x' = \gamma_v(x - vt) \quad (18)$$

$$t' = \gamma_v(t - vx/c^2) \quad (19)$$

$$y' = y \quad z' = z \quad (20)$$

Where $\gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$

From the Section 2, we can see that a photon speed remains unchanged after transforming the photon motion from frame S to frame S' by Lorentz speed transformation, i.e. Eq.(16) or (17). In the Einstein's paper [1], Einstein also verify that Maxwell's equations are Lorentz covariant, which means that after transforming Maxwell's equations from frame S to frame S' by the Lorentz transformation, the forms of Maxwell's equations can remains unchanged. It means Lorentz transformation is in accordance with the principle of relativity for transforming Maxwell's equations.

Let us study the process what Einstein did. First, Einstein assumed that after transforming Maxwell's equations from frame S to frame S' by the Lorentz transformation, the forms of Maxwell's equations remains unchanged. The Maxwell's equations in frame S are as follows [1] [4].

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \vec{E} &= \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \\ \nabla \cdot \vec{B} &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \vec{E} &= -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \vec{B} &= \mu_0 \vec{J} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

According to the principle of relativity, the Maxwell's equations in frame S' remains unchanged:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla' \cdot \vec{E}' &= \frac{\rho'}{\epsilon_0} \\ \nabla' \cdot \vec{B}' &= 0 \\ \nabla' \times \vec{E}' &= -\frac{\partial \vec{B}'}{\partial t'} \\ \nabla' \times \vec{B}' &= \mu_0' \vec{J}' - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}'}{\partial t'} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The physical quantities should be able to be transformed from frame S to frame S' by the Lorentz transformation to satisfy Eq.(22). After complex mathematical operations, Einstein gave the Lorentz transformation equations for electric and magnetic fields as follows [3]. (Note: The symbols and expression of original paper are different. See [1], page 13)

$$\begin{aligned} E'_x &= E_x & B'_x &= B_x \\ E'_y &= \gamma_v(E_y - vB_z) & B'_y &= \gamma_v(B_y + v/c^2 E_z) \\ E'_z &= \gamma_v(E_z + vB_y) & B'_z &= \gamma_v(B_z - v/c^2 E_y) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Where $\gamma_v = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$

Substituting equation (23) into equation (22), we can obtain equation (21), which means that the mathematical operation is correct. Equation (22) is called Maxwell's equations are Lorentz covariant.

Since the Lorentz transformation is in accordance with the principle of relativity, it can be applied to electromagnetic motion. Further, it is postulated that the Lorentz covariance is a physical law, and also the Lorentz covariance is applied to quantum mechanics. Moreover, the extended concept of Lorentz covariance is applied to the spacetime.

However, conforming to the principle of relativity is only the necessary condition to verify that the Lorentz transformation is correct, rather than the sufficient condition. The equation (18) and (19) only satisfy necessary condition of correctness. We need to do experiments in frame S' to verify Eq.(23), and to understand the physical meaning of E'_x, E'_y, E'_z and B'_x, B'_y, B'_z as per Eq.(23).

What are the necessary and sufficient conditions to verify the correctness of transformation equations between two reference frames? **The necessary and sufficient conditions are as follows:**

The result of transformation not only satisfies the requirements of the principle of relativity, but also satisfies the measurement values of the physical quantities in frame S' or satisfies the experimental results in frame S' or satisfies logical analysis.

For example, if the Eq.(9) is correct, the Eq.(15) should be correct according to the principle of relativity. Since the Eq.(13) and (14) contradict Eq.(15), it proves the transformation equations (5), (8) are incorrect. Similarly, if the Eq.(21) is correct, the Eq.(22) should be correct according to the principle of relativity. Since we can restore Eq.(21) after inserting Eq.(23) to Eq.(22), the Eq.(23) satisfies the necessary condition for the correctness of the transformation equations. Does Eq.(23) satisfy the sufficient condition for the correctness of the transformation equations? It depends on measurements or experiments or logical analysis.

4. Conclusion

The physical meaning of transformation equations between two reference frames: If a particle motion trajectory or motion path is known in reference frame S , we can apply transformation equations to transform the particle physical quantities (such as distance, time, velocity, momentum, etc.) from reference frame S to reference frame S' . This mathematical method can be verified by physical methods, which directly measures these physical quantities in the reference frame S' .

The distinguishing between physical time or distance and mathematical time or distance: If we transform particle physical quantities from reference frame S to reference frame S' , the t and x are physical time and physical distance, and the t' and x' are mathematical time and mathematical distance.

The motion between reference frame S' and reference frame S is symmetrical. The operation of transformation of between two reference frames is vice versa. There is no an absolute stationary frame, which is appointed by God, in the universe.

The necessary and sufficient conditions to verify the correctness of transformation equations between two reference frames: The result of transformation not only satisfies the requirements of the principle of relativity, but also satisfies the measurement values of the physical quantities in frame S' or satisfies the experimental results in frame S' or satisfies logical analysis.

As per above criterion, the Galilean transformation is incorrect, and the equations (16) and (17) are correct.

Reference:

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History Record:

This paper is the first part of a long paper. The original paper is divided into three papers.